

Robustness and Reliability of the GM Ignition Switch - A Forensic Engineering Case

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Abstract

This paper details forensic engineering from the perspectives of Robust Design and Reliability Engineering to review one of the most infamous recalls in automotive history, that of the GM ignition switch. The design, engineering and management failures in this case ultimately resulted in a fine of \$35 million, the recall of 2.6 million vehicles and the death of at least 13 people. In a systematic approach, methods such as sensitivity analysis, tolerance stack-ups, design clarity, etc., are used to analyse the ignition switch itself and to extend the usual consideration of reliability issues to the impact of variation on the design. In addition to this quantitative analysis, the legal case files have been examined revealing multiple misjudgments and errors throughout the product development process. The analysis revealed a lack of overview regarding to interrelated functionality, a lack of respect for the requirement specification and clarity in the specification itself, and finally a culture of silence rather than confrontation and remedy.

1. Introduction

The influence of engineering design decisions on the resulting product quality is indisputable. Consequently, a large number of quality methods, aiming at the assurance of functionality and the reduction of quality costs, exist. Examples are approaches such as Robust Design, Reliability analysis and Design for Six Sigma, supporting the choice of promising product solutions during the early design phases (Eifler et al. 2013). At the same time, different challenges for the application of corresponding methods exist (Krogstie et al. 2014) and the availability of quality approaches seems to be contradicted by a large number of major recalls, recently launched by big automotive OEMs. Nothing appears to have changed since Hales (2003) stated that neither basic design principles, nor corresponding methods are fully understood, accepted or used in industrial development projects.

To provide deeper insight into the causes for corresponding quality issues as well as product failures, this paper describes a forensic engineering case study of the recent and major GM ignition switch recall. Current practices of forensic engineering that appear to rely mostly on expert knowledge and experimental approaches are thereby extended by methodical reasoning, i. e. available design models and methods. In addition, the whole case is examined in terms of design activities and decisions leading up to the recall.

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1.1 Example System: GM ignition switch

The starting point for a forensic analysis of the GM ignition switch was the different headlines and news articles published by international media in the first half of 2014. Severe accidents had shown that the switch can unintentionally shut off the engine during use, also affecting airbag inflation, power steering and power brake systems. The information available indicates that the unintentional shutdown of the engine and related accessories is caused by shock loads from rough road surfaces, the driver's knee or the weight of the key chain which can knock the key out of the run position (Rogers 2014; Picchi 2014).

Following the available information, the forensic analysis of the recent recalls concentrates on the ignition switch shown in Figure 1 a). As part of the car's steering column, it is connected to the steering wheel lock, the ignition lock cylinder and consequently to the key, see Figure 1 b). The main purpose of the ignition switch is to convert the rotational movement of the key into a signal, which is sent to the Body Control Module defining the actual mode of car.

Figure 1. Example System a) Ignition Switch in b) the car's steering column

A closer look to the inside components reveals the switch's basic functionality. A movement of the key leads to a rotation of the switch plate, and thus to a change of the contact points between pins and circuit board, see Figure 2 a). While starting the car, the driver turns the switch plate to its end position "crank" allowing it then to rotate backwards. The steady modes of the car, "run" as well as "accessories", are defined by notches or "detents" in the switch plate. A plunger is forced into these detents by a spring, locking the mechanism, see Figure 2 b).

Figure 2. Product structure of a) rotating components and b) locking mechanism in the ignition switch

1.2 Forensic Engineering and related approaches

The term *Forensic Engineering* usually refers to engineers engaged in case of a threat of litigation. As expert witnesses they are investigating causes as well as the responsibility for product failures that had led to bodily injury and/or economic loss and consequently to judicial proceedings (Carper 2001). Moreover, literature emphasises the relevance of an analysis and a deeper understanding of malfunctioning products, defective buildings, etc. as information source for future projects (Carper 2001; Samuel 2007; Hales 2005). An aspect also commonly mentioned in basic literature on *Root Cause Analysis* or *Failure Diagnosis* (Andersen and Fagerhaug 2006, Carlson and Söderberg 2003). However, whereas available *Forensic Engineering* approaches are frequently reduced to experiential reasoning as well as an experimental analysis of the use conditions and the use procedure of the operator, suggested procedures for a Root Cause Analysis often focus on organisational drawbacks or business process issues (Andersen and Fagerhaug 2006).

Suggesting the technically oriented term Forensic Analysis, this paper therefore offers a far-reaching extension to the analysing procedures available. Based on methodical reasoning, the analysis of the GM ignition switch is carried out from a Robust Design/Reliability perspective¹. It has to be noted though that in contrast to a search for solutions, the proposed approach focuses solely on the analysis of an existing product. As already pointed out in Eifler (2014) the complexity of the product under investigation is specifically reduced by means of suitable product and/or process descriptions offering insight into relevant characteristics and noise factors.

2. Forensic analysis of the GM ignition switch – a technical perspective

The analysis of the GM ignition switch is structured into five subsequent steps. First of all, failure modes of the switch, potentially leading to accidents, are identified based on the available information. Afterwards, the qualitative description is concretised by a first rough mathematical description of the failure mechanism, i. e. the governing equation. An analysis of the device at the system level, e.g. the consideration of relevant product characteristics in a linear tolerance chain or the detailed investigation of possible variation at part interfaces, is then extended to the description of unforeseen noise factors in a P-Diagram. Concluding, the importance of different influencing factors is evaluated in a sensitivity analysis.

2.1 Identification of potential failure modes

Approaches to support the identification and prioritisation of potential failure modes in a (complex) product system are usually largely qualitative. By means of an Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA), a Failure Tree Analysis (FTA), Flow charts, etc. (Eifler et al. 2013, Andersen and Fagerhaug 2006), the product is structured into different parts or its functions/sub-functions and potential failures are assessed. However, in the case of the GM recall, the information available already allows for an identification of the ignition switch's locking mechanism as one of the most relevant aspects of the overall system. In contrast to starting problems reported early in the switch's life cycle², a malfunction of the locking mechanism could lead to an abrupt change of the car mode and thus to severe safety issues.

2.2 Governing equation – Screening of relevant influences

As already seen in Figure 2, the rotating switch plate which defines the contact points to the circuit board is locked by means of a detent plunger. Forced into notches by the compression of an additional spiral spring, the plunger holds the switch plate in place and defines the steady power modes of the vehicle, i. e. “run” and “accessories”. The switch's basic functionality can consequently be described by Coulomb's law of friction, see Figure 3 a). If the applied horizontal force exceeds the force at the contact surface, the locking mechanism fails and switch plate as well as key are knocked out of position.

¹Ebro et al. (2012) and Eifler et al. (2013) summarise Robust Design or Reliability Engineering methods.

²Customer Complaints and warranty claims regarding starting problems of cars could be traced back to the ignition switch in an intensive investigation shortly after it was firstly used in the GM Ion production in 2002. Especially in cold ambient conditions, the behaviour of the used grease affected the connection between contact pins on the switch plate and the circuit board (Committee of Energy & Commerce 2014).

Figure 3. Simplified description of the switch's basic mechanical concept

A simplified mathematical description of the switch's basic mechanical concept allows for the first rough assessment of potential root causes for product failures by means of a quantitative analysis. Neglecting potential self locking effects between plunger and switch plate, the different parameters affecting the locking mechanism are summarised in equation 1.

$$F > F_H = F_v \frac{\tan \theta + \mu}{1 - \mu \cdot \tan \theta} \quad (1)$$

The generated holding force F_H is affected by the force of the plunger in vertical direction, the angle of the notches θ and the surface roughness μ . Extended by a decomposition of the plunger force F_v into the characteristics of the spiral spring utilised, i. e. the spring constant k_c as well as its compression $s = l_1 - l_2$ shown in Figure 3 b), the impact of potential deviations from a specified nominal value can be calculated. However, as any information about the ingoing variation is more an assumption than actual knowledge at such an early stage of the analysis, the calculation is reduced to a first estimate of the basic sensitivity. This change of the response value F_H due to a percentage change of the different input factors is summarised in Figure 4.

Parameters		Input				Response (force F_H)			Sensitivity		
		Nominal	1%-Var.	5%-Var.	SI	Nominal	ΔF (1%)	ΔF (5%)	SI	1%-Var.	5%-Var.
θ	Angle of notches	0,92	0,0092	0,0460	Rad	4,46	0,1157	0,6345	N	2,59	2,84
k_c	Spring constant	0,7	0,0070	0,0350	N/mm		0,0446	0,2232	N	1,00	1,00
s	Compression of spring (in groove)	2,74	0,0274	0,1370	mm		0,0446	0,2232	N	1,00	1,00
μ	coefficient of friction	0,25	0,0025	0,0125			0,0291	0,1484	N	0,65	0,66

Figure 4. Simplified description of the switch's basic mechanical concept

By the calculation of sensitivity indices the relevance of geometric variation becomes apparent. An example is a potentially varying compression of the spring, where a one percent change of the length Δs leads to a corresponding change of the resulting force ΔF_H . The same holds true for the spring characteristic which is, next to the material properties, also defined by its' geometry. Of particular importance seem to be the geometry of the notches. As indicated in Figure 4 by the sensitivity values for a one as well as a five percent change, an angle variation $\Delta \theta$ significantly increases the resulting variation of the holding force and moreover does not show a linear behaviour. The wider the range of the ingoing variation is, the more sensitive the locking mechanism reacts. In contrast, the impact of a varying surface roughness $\Delta \mu$, seems to be negligible and is in case of a potential contact to both sides of the notch even reduced further due to self-locking effects.

2.3 System modelling – Analysis of dimensional and geometric variations

Sensitivity calculations by means of the governing equation allow for a first prioritisation of potentially varying influences. However, the result of this largely simplified analysis must on the one hand be verified, ideally by measurements of physical samples. On the other hand, a further decomposition of single influences is necessary. Especially in case of (complex) product systems, a large number

of parts and their interactions need to be examined.

In the forensic analysis of the ignition switch, two easy to measure dimensions were chosen for verification purposes. For ten samples, measurements of a single component as well the assembled device, i. e. the height of the lower housing h_1 and the overall height h_2 , were taken, see Figure 5 a). A comparison with the specified nominal value³ thereby supports the assumption that geometric variations might be the root cause for the occurred product failures. Although dimensions of single components often seem to be under their specification level, the measured height of the assembled device persistently exceeds the specified nominal value as shown in Figure 5 b) and c).

Figure 5. Measurement of a) physical samples and comparison of the b) component or b) device dimensions to specified nominal values

Accordingly, an in-depth analysis of geometric variations at the systems level needs to be performed following the measurement of physical samples. The first step is the calculation of a linear tolerance chain in axial direction since the displacement of the switch plate is very much dependent on the varying compression of the used spring. Relevant components and interfaces are shown by a cross section in Figure 6 a) including the rotating parts as well as the plunger.

Figure 6. Linear tolerance chain in a) a cross section and b) the quantitative analysis

Based on the assumption of an IT-grade 13 for all dimensions (A, B, C)⁴, a tolerance stack up calculation allows for a prediction of potential extreme cases, i. e. a maximum/minimum deviation of the distance between upper housing and switch plate (D) of $\pm 0,31$ mm. The results, shown in Figure 6 b), lead to a symmetric interval for the variation of the holding force $\Delta F_H = \pm 0,51$ N, i. e. a deviation of 11% from the nominal value provided that the other parameters in equation (1) remain constant. However, although dimensional tolerance stack-up calculations are widely used and offer an initial overview about part interactions at the systems level, they can be highly misleading. Essential

³Whereas the dimensions of the ignition switch were identified in a Reverse Engineering approach, i. e. based on measurements of physical samples, additional documents on nominal values as well as potential shortcomings during the development or the approval process are accessible as part of an official congressional hearing, see for example Committee of Energy & Commerce (2014).

⁴The assumption is based on the ISO code system for tolerances on linear sizes (ISO 286-2 2010).

aspects of the occurring variation as well as potential drawbacks of the design are for example completely neglected. Firstly, the analysis is therefore usually extended to a calculation of the Root Square Sum (RSS), also shown in Figure 6 b), assuming that most of the components fall to the mid of the specified value range rather than in its' extreme ends. Secondly, and particularly important from a Robust Design perspective, a consideration of geometric tolerances is necessary as the functional relevance of variation largely depends on the geometry of interfaces/active surfaces rather than on single dimensions.

For simplification purposes and because basic Robust Design Principles seem to have been ignored in case of the ignition switch, this paper refers to the Design Clarity approach elaborated by Ebro et al. (2012) instead of to a full calculation of geometric tolerances. Accordingly, robustness issues of the switch's design can be attributed to the large contact surfaces between parts, e. g. between upper and lower housing or between housing and switch plate as illustrated in Figure 7 a) and b). These consequently ambiguous interfaces lead to a product which is highly sensitive to geometric variations and thus might affect the overall functionality of the ignition switch.

Figure 7. Large contact surfaces between a) upper and lower housing, b) housing and rotating switch plate

2.4 P-Diagram – Identification of unexpected influences during use

Next to an analysis of the design itself as well as of the potential geometric variation due to manufacturing inaccuracies, a comprehensive forensic analysis also requires a deeper understanding of interdependencies between the product and the varying use conditions. Using a basic tool from Robust Design approaches potentially varying influencing factors are thus identified and visualised by means of a P-diagram, see Figure 8 a). Based on the consideration of the switch's functionality in section 2.2 that has shown a direct connection between the locking mechanism and the key movement, the analysis focusses on loads applied unexpectedly during use. An unintentional contact with the driver might for example increase the probability that the key is knocked out of position. Another possibility is an additional torque which results from an excessive weight of the key chain F_{key} and is at the same time influenced by the geometry key ring as well as of the key itself, i. e. the opening for the key ring, as shown by the resulting length l_1 in Figure 8 b).

Figure 8. Analysis of unexpected influences a) using the P-diagram and b) calculation of unexpected loads at the key ring

2.5 Sampling based analysis of the GM ignition switch

The forensic analysis of the ignition switch suggests that the basic failure mode is purely mechanical. If the key torque T_{key} , or respectively the corresponding force F applied to the locking mechanism, exceeds the varying holding force F_H , the key is knocked out of position. The analysis of the governing equation (1) can thus be easily extended to a simplified, sampling based, robustness orientated analysis of the ignition switch in varying use conditions. Taking into account the relevance of different surface geometries, the varying force limits which would lead to a sudden and unintended change of the vehicle's power mode are calculated. In addition to extended information about geometric variation, i. e. the achievable flatness of large surfaces⁵, extreme cases for the position of the key chain are considered leading to an average force limit of $F = 6,63 \text{ N}$ and a corresponding standard deviation of $\sigma = 0,41 \text{ N}$ in a worst case scenario, see Figure 9 a). Instead of the expected reliability, the transmitted variation is calculated afterwards. The results in Figure 9 b) indicate that two main drivers are decisive for an analysis of the occurring variation from a Robust Design perspective. In the first place, the ignition switch is highly sensitive to a variation of the spring compression s , i. e. of the dimensions and geometries. Moreover, potential forces during use, e. g. the variation of the key chain position l_1 , need to be analysed further.

Figure 9. Identification of a) force limits and b) the transmitted variation

4. Conclusion

A large number of major recalls, recently launched by big automotive OEMs, suggest that basic design principles as well as available design methods and tools, specifically aiming at an increased product quality, are neither used nor fully understood in industrial practice. This paper, therefore, offers an overview about one of the most infamous recalls in automotive history, that of the GM ignition switch. The proposed, far reaching extension of usual Forensic Engineering and Root Cause Analysis practices by available design approaches offers a comprehensive overview about relevant design-, production- as well as use-related influences potentially leading to product failures.

The performed case study shows that especially the application of Robust Design methods and tools, such as Design Clarity, P-Diagrams, sensitivity studies, etc., in extension to basic reliability techniques allows for deeper insight into the switch's functionality and the impact of variation. It seems as if the case files regarding the recall tend to ignore that fact that the switch had large variations in performance (indicating a lack of robustness) and instead focused purely on the analysis of the "nominal design". Moreover, when deconstructing the whole case in terms of the design activities and decisions leading up to the recall, it becomes evident where current reliability engineering techniques are failing to be deployed or not solving the reliability issues faced and is dealt with in more detail in forthcoming publications.

⁵In addition to the general dimensional tolerance windows of the ISO 286-2 (2010) standard, guidelines of the American society of the plastic industry are used (SPI 1998). For further information on dimensions of the switch and the performed analysis see also the downloads on www.RobustDesign.org/ISoRD

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